

Beyond HM Treasury's Green Book – From Auxiliary to Core: New Project Governance for Climate-Contested Land Use Projects through the Open-Praxis-Graph Research Methodology

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Abstract:

Public-sector infrastructure projects are increasingly shaped by the intersecting crises of climate breakdown, biodiversity and ecology loss, and digitally enabled dissent. In this paper, I introduce the term 'Climate-Contested Land Use Projects' (CCLUPs) to capture a novel project typology defined by ecological risk, democratic challenge, and institutional fragility. These contested arenas of infrastructure decision-making expose the epistemic and moral limitations of dominant conventional capital investment manuals such as those exemplified by HM Treasury's Green Book, which, rooted in utilitarian neoclassic economic abstraction privileges short-term monetary value over intergenerational equity and ecological sustainability.

To address this gap, I develop and apply the Open-Praxis-Graph (O-P-G) as a Transdisciplinary Research Methodology (TRM). O-P-G conjoins three umbrella concepts as terms of art: open digital data (Open), practice-based social ontology (Praxis), and Graph (semantic network analysis informed by graph theory). Applied to the National Health Service (NHS) Velindre Cancer Centre, a paradigmatic CCLUP,

I interrogate the interplay of affective protest, institutional inertia, and pluralistic norms during its front-end project phase.

My findings reveal how digitally mediated dissent and contested material entanglements reshape governance logics in ways not accounted for by conventional investment manuals such as the Green Book. The O-P-G as a TRM renders such social dynamics visible in real time, offering a participatory epistemic framework that foregrounds affect, ethics, and democratic legitimacy.

In aligning with SEEDS 2025's imperative to reposition sustainability as a core requirement rather than as an auxiliary consideration, I contend that both new methodologies and ontological clarity are required to rethink land-use governance under the pressures of the Anthropocene. O-P-G as a TRM thus contributes to policy reform and project studies by challenging technocratic orthodoxy and affirming the necessity of transdisciplinary, value-sensitive inquiry.

Keywords: Climate-Contested Land Use Projects, Social Ontology, Epistemic Governance, Open-Praxis-Graph as a Transdisciplinary Research Methodology.

1. Introduction - Setting the Stage

The 2025 SEEDS Conference issues a pointed provocation: that sustainability must no longer be treated as an auxiliary concern, but repositioned as a core political, ethical, and epistemological priority. This essay responds to that provocation by framing a new typology of sustainable development dispute-Climate Contested Land-Use Projects (CCLUPs)-and proposing a novel transdisciplinary research methodology¹ (TRM) for their analysis and understanding. I conceptualise CCLUPs as a social phenomenon observed first-hand (O’Keeffe, et al., 2025, Forthcoming) to emerge as a paradoxical duality: the urgent demand for socially valuable infrastructure-such as hospitals, housing, energy, and flood resilience-versus the moral imperative to preserve biodiversity and ecological integrity, as enshrined in progressive legislation such as the Well-being of Future Generations (Wales) Act (2015) and the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Uncertainties and stakes are high: we are witnessing not only worsening ecological collapse but also a disturbing trend among liberal democracies-including the UK-towards top-down, growth-oriented planning regimes that marginalise public deliberation and ecological responsibility (Hulme, 2011; Flyvbjerg and Gardner, 2023).

In this polarised terrain, I argue that traditional UK public-sector project evaluation frameworks, mandated as policy by HM Treasury’s long-established Green Book, and those similar mandates used elsewhere in other democracies, are no longer fit for purpose for CCLUPs.

This essay argues that CCLUPs are symptomatic of deeper epistemic and moral failures within contemporary UK infrastructure project governance, and that addressing them requires an innovative transdisciplinary methodological shift toward participatory, practice-informed evaluation research methodology, such as the Open-Praxis-Graph (O-P-G) methodology.

I argue the case for O-P-G used as an innovative TRM-that is anti-Cartesian, anti-foundational, and emancipatory-and that enables more ethical, intergenerational engagement with land-

¹ In this essay, I appropriate Lang’s definition: A transdisciplinary research methodology integrates academic knowledge with societal practices through collaboration across disciplines and with non-academic actors to address complex, real-world problems (Lang et al., 2012), and thus by extension, the collaboration of ‘experts’ and ‘non-experts’ for clarity.

use contested sustainability projects. O-P-G as a TRM is grounded in qualitative practice theory and recent developments in quantitative graph theory but extends to resonate with post-normal science (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993), citizen science², and deliberative democratic innovations like Ireland's and New Zealand's Citizens' Assemblies specifically for biodiversity (Lennon, 2024; Ní Shúilleabháin et al., 2023). In contrast to the increasingly authoritarian tendencies of the current UK government, I claim that if used as an interrogative TRM, O-P-G affirms practical intelligibility³—the sense of what makes sense to do in a given situation, shaped by the social practices in which stakeholders in such CCLUPs are immersed (Schatzki, 1996, 2002)—as well as other affordances such as participatory graphical visualisation and post-Cartesian epistemologies.

Two major externalities—digitalisation and the moral imperative of the climate crisis (Hormio, 2023)—shape the epistemic field in which today's CCLUPs unfold. Digitalisation, via the 'Triple Revolution' (internet, mobile, social media) (Rainie and Wellman, 2012) and the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Schwab, 2016), has transformed public discourse, protest, civil disobedience and collective intelligence. The climate crisis, meanwhile, has evolved into a civilisational and intergenerational moral challenge (Gardiner, 2011; IPCC, 2022). These forces foster CCLUPs as a distinct social phenomenon—irreducible to and typologically distinct from NIMBYism or conventional or traditional and more general analogue-based environmental opposition.

CCLUPs arise from a paradox: the urgent demand for socially valuable infrastructure (e.g., hospitals, schools, reservoirs, transport and energy systems) coexists with the imperative to preserve biodiversity and ecology. Radical Flank Climate Activists (RFCAs)—including Extinction Rebellion, Just Stop Oil, Le Soulèvement de la Terre (SLT) and Blockade Australia—have intensified this tension through digitally enabled civil disobedience and physical protest. These movements ground their practice in normative theories of resistance (Thoreau, 1849; Rawls, 1971) while skilfully using open-source tactics and algorithmic mobilisation (Williams & Rudd, 2024). Protests like those by SLT in France and Blockade Australia exemplify the transnational, strategic nature of CCLUP contestation (Morin, 2023; Hutley, 2022). Delays and

² Citizen science refers to the involvement of non-professionals in the process of scientific research—ranging from data collection to analysis and dissemination—often enhancing scientific literacy and participatory governance (Bonney et al., 2009; Follett & Strezov, 2015; Salmon et al., 2021).

³ For further clarity, Schatzki, from whom this term originates, also refers to the material arrangements that are an essential consideration of the material and physical context surrounding such decisions acting also as the sense-making structures that enable individuals to recognise what actions make sense to do next in a given context (Schatzki, 2002).

inflationary costs from such disruption to socially valuable often badly needed public sector infrastructure projects are significant (O’Keeffe, et al., 2025, Forthcoming).

This essay positions itself not as an abstract critique, but as a transdisciplinary methodological intervention. It adopts the form of a conceptual essay, organised through narrative exposition, metaphorical contrast, and final synthesis. A dramaturgical framing (Goffman, 1959; Feyerabend, 1975; Latour, 1996) and allegorical cinematic metaphor from the film, *Tár*, (Field, 2022) surface the moral and epistemic dissonances in UK sustainability governance. A central device is the juxtaposition in a pivotal scene in this film between Lydia Tár’s hierarchical worldview-representing HM Treasury orthodoxy-and the digitally conscious, eco-anxious perspective of Generation Alpha and Z younger generations, represented by Max.

This intervention critiques the extant Green Book-HM Treasury’s long-established evaluative business-case cornerstone that underpins all UK public-sector infrastructure capital investment decisions. Its deterministic logic and reliance on monetised outcomes render it, however necessary, epistemologically insufficient to address today’s moral and ecological complexities (Flyvbjerg and Gardner, 2023) that surface in CCLUPs. CCLUPs show that such narrow, mandated and prescribed quantitative economic methodologies that underpin the Green Book are no longer tenable. The civic resistance surrounding these projects, compounded by legislative reforms under the UK Government’s ‘Growth Agenda’, demands a new form of deliberative democratic civic engagement-one that prioritises understanding over prediction, participation over compliance, and transparency over a technocratic ideal of public value⁴.

O-P-G as a TRM is offered not as a replacement for policy tools, such as the Green Book and those like it, but as a counter-anti-foundational, supplementary methodology-a means to map and critically reflect on the practices and meanings that constitute a land-use contested project’s social reality. Used as an interrogative transdisciplinary method, it affirms practical intelligibility, participatory visualisation, and post-Cartesian epistemologies. It aligns with calls by scholars like Unterhitzberger, McKiernan and Huemann (2024) for ‘responsible research’ and evaluative frames adequate to the moral, ecological, and democratic challenges of our time.

The thesis of this essay is therefore clear: CCLUPs are not anomalies; they signal paradigmatic failure. They compel us, as responsible and ethical researchers, to confront failures of sustainable development that should no longer be treated as an auxiliary concern.

⁴ A technocratic ideal of public value refers to the belief that complex societal goods can be adequately captured and governed through technical metrics, models, and expertise, often to the exclusion of deliberative or pluralistic forms of valuation (Mazzucato, 2018; Coyle, 2020)

In sum, this essay unfolds a reflection on biodiversity and ecology loss in the UK as a pressing sustainability issue and societal concern beyond the UK. It proceeds through conceptual premises, counterpoints, and synthesis, culminating in a call to reimagine project governance in CCLUPs not as control, but as collaborative understanding amid uncertainty. The essay references two recent UK CCLUPs as empirical anchors to illustrate how O-P-G as a TRM can assist researchers and project managers to promote sustainable development aligned with the SDGs and legislation like the Well-Being of Future Generations Act (Wales) 2015, as being optimistically contemplated elsewhere in several enlighten democracies⁵.

2. Determinism and its Discontent

Determinism⁶ has long underpinned the UK's approach to public sector project appraisal. Rooted in the traditions of economic rationalism and technocratic governance, deterministic policy prescriptions as mandated presume that future outcomes can be predicted, modelled, and optimised through quantifiable inputs. In sustainability governance, this logic is institutionalised most prominently in HM Treasury's Green Book. As the official guidance for business case development, the Green Book enshrines principles of 'value for money' that privilege monetised metrics, cost-benefit ratios, and measurable risk mitigation strategies. These principles, while internally coherent, have become increasingly contested in the face of complex climate-related projects that challenge the predict-and-control paradigm.

The dominance of HM Treasury-established in 1126 and unique among democracies for combining economic policy design with fiscal gatekeeping (Easton, 2020; Kay, 2003)-has entrenched a technocratic rationalism that persists despite rhetorical reform. The 2020 *Green Book* revisions, while invoking place-based value and strategic alignment, preserve the primacy of benefit-cost ratios and discount rates (but also moral compression⁷) (HM Treasury, 2020; Coyle and Sensier, 2020). As Collier (2018) notes, this logic has roots in post-war Britain's utilitarian vanguard, which bulldozed communities in the name of efficiency-only to face moral backlash. He draws on Haidt's (2012) moral foundations theory to argue that values like care, fairness, loyalty, and sanctity were systematically ignored. These historical tensions, I submit, have re-emerged again, in Labour's 2025 Planning and Infrastructure Bill,

⁵ Examples include Scotland, New Zealand, Finland, Ireland, Iceland, and jurisdictions within Canada and the European Union, all of which have either adopted or are actively exploring intergenerational sustainability frameworks modelled in part on the Welsh Government's Well-being of Future Generations Act (2015)

⁶ Determinism in economic evaluation refers to the presumption that outcomes can be predicted with certainty from known variables, often through models such as cost-benefit analysis, which may overlook uncertainty, plural values, and socio-ecological complexity (Spash, 2021).

⁷ Discount rates and moral compression: Discounting future benefits and harms in cost-benefit analysis compresses moral time by systematically devaluing long-term environmental and intergenerational consequences, often privileging short-term economic rationality over ecological justice (Gowdy et al., 2010; Treich, 2020)

which seeks to fast-track growth amid warnings from the Office for Environmental Protection that legal safeguards for habitats and public consent may be bypassed (The Guardian, 2025a; 2025b). Efficiency without empathy remains a path-dependent⁸ governance flaw.

The origins of this deterministic legacy can be traced to mid-twentieth century systems thinking and positivist economics, which viewed the state as a paternal rational actor, capable of optimising social outcomes through mechanistic planning. In the UK, the Green Book evolved out of this tradition. Its framework encourages linear planning logic: define a problem, evaluate options, assign monetary values, and select the most efficient solution. Although recent revisions (e.g., HM Treasury, 2020) have attempted to broaden the framework by including non-monetary considerations such as well-being, these remain subordinate to economic optimisation logics. As Flyvbjerg and Gardner (2023) argue, such approaches frequently underestimate complexity, ignore emergent stakeholder dynamics, and obscure epistemic uncertainty.

Nowhere are these limitations more evident than in the appraisal of CCLUPs. These projects—often large-scale infrastructure schemes with high ecological impact—exemplify the clash between long-term sustainability imperatives and short-term economic priorities. The deterministic framing of the Green Book tends to silence pluralistic knowledge systems and local moral claims, especially those mobilised by Radical Flank Climate Activists. These activists challenge not only the substantive outcomes of projects but the very epistemology by which such outcomes are justified. In doing so, they confront the hegemony of metrics-based rationality (Chamberlain and Madsen, 2025; Berglund and Schmidt, 2020; Kenward and Brick, 2024).

Crucially, the problem with deterministic frameworks is not merely technical but ontological. As Schatzki (2002; 2025) notes, social life is constituted by interwoven practices, material arrangements, and forms of intelligibility that cannot be fully captured by computational models. To impose a linear logic of causality on CCLUPs is to misrecognise their performative, affective, and contested nature. It also ignores the historical and moral dimensions of Land-Use conflicts, which often invoke legacies of colonialism, dispossession, and ecological extraction.

Moreover, deterministic governance frameworks exacerbate legitimacy crises. When local communities and activists find their concerns omitted from official appraisals, they are more likely to reject the process altogether. This delegitimisation feeds a spiral of mistrust and resistance. As Hulme (2011) observes, climate governance is as much about meaning-making

⁸ Path-dependence refers to a condition in which earlier institutional choices or structural constraints limit future options, making change difficult or costly. Often linked to deterministic perspectives, it explains how governance systems may persist with suboptimal or ethically problematic practices due to historical momentum, sunk costs, or institutional inertia (Pierson, P. (2000).

and political contestation as it is about emissions targets or cost projections. The refusal to acknowledge this complexity within deterministic policy models is a structural weakness that undermines public trust and democratic deliberation.

Even efforts to embed resilience and well-being metrics within deterministic systems remain constrained by their underlying logic. For example, the Green Book's inclusion of distributional analysis and natural capital valuation still relies on the commensuration of diverse goods into monetary equivalents. Such attempts may soften the edges of technocracy, but they do not transform its epistemic core. As Latour (1996) has demonstrated through his sociotechnical ethnographies, the politics of calculation often obscure the moral and relational choices embedded in technological systems.

From a methodological standpoint, this section highlights a critical juncture: either we continue to refine deterministic systems in the hope of marginal improvement, or we adopt a fundamentally different stance. The latter does not entail the abandonment of rigour, but a recalibration of what rigour means. Feyerabend (1975) would argue that the pluralisation of method-including narrative, allegory, and dissent-is essential to intellectual progress. In this spirit, the essay turns next to an alternative approach: O-P-G as a TRM, which seeks to reclaim intelligibility, plurality, and participation as central to project appraisal.

In summary, deterministic frameworks like the Green Book are shown to be historically and at the current time structurally misaligned with the nature of CCLUPs. Their reliance on prediction, commensuration, and linear causality may make them necessary but it renders them epistemically brittle and ethically insufficient. By contrast, alternative methodologies such as O-P-G as a TRM that embrace uncertainty, multiplicity, and engagement offer a more fitting response to the challenges of UK and beyond sustainable development in a contested, pluralistic world by supplementing the Green Book and those that share its methodology when CCLUPs are encountered.

3. The Praxis of Participation: O-P-G as a TRM

Building on the critique of deterministic rationality above, this section deepens the ontological and epistemological grounding of O-P-G as a TRM. Rather than reintroducing it, the focus here is to elaborate its conceptual depth and empirical utility in navigating CCLUPs. O-P-G's three conjoined terms-Open, Praxis, and Graph-work conceptually as umbrella terms of art in concert to expose and interrogate the underlying activity chains, affective tensions, and epistemic contradictions of contested land-use infrastructure proposals. Together, they offer not merely a representational lens, but an ethically attuned, practice-grounded, graphically mediated methodological mode of inquiry.

The first of these three conceptual umbrella terms of art, "Open" reflects both a normative commitment to transparency and inclusivity, and a methodological openness to the

naturalistic affordances of openly and publicly available online digital data-social media campaigns, planning submission and other websites, online newspapers, and activist discourses (amongst others) that disrupt closed, model-driven technocracy.

“Praxis”, draws on a Wittgensteinian–Heideggerian–Schatzkian account of materially situated, embodied activity. Here, practical intelligibility- i.e. “what makes sense to do” for a person at a particular moment, as shaped by their participation in a practice, the material arrangements they encounter, and the teleoaffective structures⁹ guiding their actions (Schatzki, 2002, p. 80) - not abstract variables-becomes the central unit of analysis.

“Graph” as the final umbrella conceptual term of art, incorporates graph theory and network science, (Barabási, 2016) not as an abstraction, but as a way to visually articulate the temporal, relational, and material dynamics emerging from empirical engagements. Its visual vocabulary communicates complexity without simplification, supporting plural participation in deliberative settings (Watts, 2004; Newman, 2010). These nodes and edges of these graphs are not abstracted in the manner of traditional social network analysis; instead, they are grounded in ethnographic and discursive data extracted from meetings, workshops, interviews, and publicly available online project documents (e.g. minutes of meetings, drawings, business cases, programmes, Freedom of Information Requests, amongst others).

What distinguishes O-P-G from other methodologies derived from graph theory is its focus on practical intelligibility-appropriated from Schatzki's practice theory, on tracing how actors make sense of their actions and obligations amid uncertainty and disagreement. In this sense, O-P-G is not only descriptive but normative. It reveals whose voices are amplified, whose practices are considered legitimate, and which arrangements facilitate or frustrate collaborative sense-making. In doing so, it challenges the epistemic closure of the dominant appraisal tools of HM Treasury orthodoxies.

Together, these overarching conceptual elements support an innovative research methodology that is simultaneously empirical, analytical, ethical, deliberative and as it is intended to be transdisciplinary, can be emancipatory. A full theoretical defence of O-P-G's ontological commensurability as a research methodology is beyond the scope of this section but its genesis, and its specific application, and empirical substantialisation, focussed on the use of social and online news media, has been illustrated via the on-going NHS New National Cancer Centre project in Wales as a recent UK case-study (O’Keeffe et al., 2025, Forthcoming). While the project was justified using Green Book-compliant logic, it sparked digital activism under the #SaveTheNorthernMeadows campaign becoming a CCLUP. Applying a specific configuration of an analytical perspective to what later has evolved into O-P-G as a TRM, researchers mapped the divergent activity chains: health planners defending timelines;

⁹ Teleoaffective structures refer to the configurations of ends, purposes, emotions, and moods that guide and give meaning to practical activity within social practices (Schatzki, 2002)

activists mobilising ecological care; and digital platforms amplifying generational affect. Practical intelligibility emerged not from metrics, but from competing, morally charged enactments of place, legacy, and obligation.

Similarly, the proposed Woodhouse Colliery in Cumbria exemplifies another UK CCLUP. Approved in December 2022 to support steelmaking with 'net zero' claims via offsetting, the project faced fierce resistance from climate scientists, legal scholars, and NGOs. Willis (2024) demonstrates how evidence was selectively mobilised, creating a 'false balance' that favoured economic justifications despite substantial counterevidence. If applied, using openly available online data, O-P-G would render visible these dynamics by tracing, using publically available online data, the interplay between technical rationales, performative politics, and material contradictions. When the mine was withdrawn in April 2025 following legal challenges and policy shifts, it exposed not just policy failure, but the epistemic fragility of linear appraisal logics.

In stark contrast to deterministic methodologies like HM Treasury's Green Book, O-P-G does not implicitly or otherwise try to predict outcomes of CCLUPs via optimisation logics. Instead, it attends to the understanding and thereby insights into their social dynamics, - the fluid interplay of actors, logics, and objects-revealing not what "should happen" economically, but what *is happening* socially and ethically, in near real-time, within its project practices. It privileges understanding (*verstehen*) over prediction (*erklären*) -not seeking to model outcomes but to understand trajectories, tensions, and teleoaffective commitments. It creates space for what I term as *pre-dialogical intelligibility*-the surfacing of submerged logics before formal deliberation begins. Theoretically, O-P-G as TRM aligns with Post-Normal Science¹⁰ (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993), which emphasises deliberation under high uncertainty and contested values.

Importantly, O-P-G also embodies a situated ethics of research. It supports what Unterhitzberger et al. (2024) calls the responsible researcher - one who is reflexively aware of their positionality, and committed to enabling ethically and morally shared sense-making, rather than asserting interpretive dominance.

Finally, it is important to stress that O-P-G does not propose a wholesale replacement of the Green Book. Rather, it offers a critical supplement - one that addresses the Green Book's blind spots during CCLUPs by embedding teleoaffective structures, plural values, and inclusive

¹⁰ Post-normal science (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993) emerges in contexts where facts are uncertain, values are in dispute, stakes are high, and decisions are urgent - characteristics found to be empirically typical of CCLUPs. It advocates inclusive, deliberative, and pluralistic modes of inquiry.

temporalities into land-use governance decision-making. In doing so, it contributes to a more just, transparent, long-term and ecologically literate public infrastructure discourse.

4. *Tár* as Allegory: Dramaturgy and Generational Conflict

If the two preceding sections of this essay addressed, respectively, the discursive and methodological crises afflicting land-use governance, this section shifts terrain to dramatise a generational and moral-epistemological rupture. Drawing on the film *Tár* (Field, 2022), the analysis mobilises allegory not as empirical evidence but as a heuristic device—one that illuminates latent tensions between inherited systems of authority and emergent ethical demands that distinctly characterise CCLUPs. Lydia *Tár*, a conductor committed to canonical order and elite virtuosity, serves here as a metaphor for the modernist project of technocratic governance: brilliant, commanding, but insulated from the evolving sensibilities of the communities she ostensibly serves. Her much younger adversary, Max, does not contest the aesthetic structure of musical excellence per se, but rather its ethical vacuity and its immunity to critique. This staged conflict in the pivotal scene from the film distils the dramaturgical dynamics of contested infrastructure projects, where appeals to expertise, legacy, or public value often clash with affective, moral, and generational claims.

The scene in which Max disengages from the rehearsal over the moral legacy of composers like Bach becomes emblematic—not for its specific content, but for its structural resonance. The refusal to separate technical brilliance from moral responsibility echoes broader societal refusals to accept the epistemic authority of institutions whose legitimacy has eroded. However, this resonance ought to be handled with care: *Tár* is an allegory, not an empirical source. Its power lies in its condensation of affective and epistemological dissonance, not in its fidelity to climate politics or planning practice.

This reflects the wider performativity at play in many land-use conflicts, where deliberation is scripted, authority staged, and complexity reduced to procedural closure. As Baudrillard (1994) argued, modern public-sector project governance increasingly operates through *simulacra*—representations that obscure rather than reveal reality. In the context of Climate-Contested Land Use Projects (CCLUPs), this can be seen in the mobilisation of consultation theatre and sustainability branding that strips contestations of their intergenerational and moral stakes, re-scripted instead in the language of compromise and institutional deference. In this sense, the Lydia–Max allegory stages not only generational divergence, but also ontological dissonance between performative governance and affective dissent.

O-P-G as a TRM speaks into this conflict—not by taking sides, but by rendering the contest visible. It does not demand allegiance to expertise nor an abandonment of rational appraisal. Rather, it acknowledges the performativity of governance—its dramaturgical logics, affective economies, and symbolic claims to legitimacy. In the context of CCLUPs, such dramaturgy is not ornamental; it is constitutive.

Yet the voices that dramatise this dissonance—Radical Flank Activists, digitally mobilised publics, disenfranchised communities—have not (as yet) adopted O-P-G as a TRM. That is unsurprising. However, they do operate through modalities resonant with its principles. For instance, Extinction Rebellion’s civil disobedience playbook (Berglund and Schmidt, 2020) promotes direct action grounded in ecological grief, affective urgency, and distributed agency. These are not statistical inputs; they are world-disclosing practices. They refuse the reduction of “matters of concern¹¹” to calculation, of dissent to noise.

The stakes of this refusal are existential. The reality of a sixth mass extinction—grounded in robust scientific consensus (Ceballos, Ehrlich and Raven, 2020)—renders traditional appraisal frameworks not merely insufficient but ethically obtuse. It is no longer a matter of refining tools, but of recognising that the tools themselves may be inadequate to the scale, affect, and temporality of planetary crisis.

In sum, this section does not celebrate Tár’s downfall nor Max’s defiance. Rather, it vividly surfaces the theatricality of legitimacy and the contested ethics of authority found empirically and in practice in CCLUPs. O-P-G does not resolve such social contests over land-use decisions, but it creates space for it—space to visualise, map, and morally appraise the collisions between generational obligation and institutional inertia. In doing so, it helps reimagine the distinctions of the stage upon which such decisions about land-use, biodiversity and ecological loss and in turn planetary futures are enacted.

5. HM Treasury, the Dasgupta Review, and the Persistence of Economic Orthodoxy

This section critically assesses the epistemic positioning of HM Treasury and its commissioned flagship *Dasgupta Review on the Economics of Biodiversity* (2021). Despite the Review’s rhetorical embrace of ecological complexity, much of its content remains wedded to neoclassical economic reasoning, operationalised through cost–benefit analysis, discounting, and the formalism of natural capital accounting. While the Review generated considerable political attention, including endorsements from global finance leaders and environmental organisations, its conceptual infrastructure remains underpinned by the same technocratic rationalities that have historically excluded non-economic valuations of nature.

As Groom and Turk (2022) note, Dasgupta’s attempt to internalise ecological limits within an “inclusive wealth” framework paradoxically affirms the same quantification logics that sustain extractive paradigms. Natural capital models presuppose the commensurability of ecological

¹¹ Matters of concern, as opposed to matters of fact, represent issues that gather public attention, controversy, and affective significance—emphasising the relational and contested nature of scientific and political knowledge (Latour, 2004)

functions, rendering biodiversity legible primarily in terms of its instrumental value. Spash (2021) is unequivocal: such approaches fail to recognise the ontological distinctiveness of ecological systems and reinforce an illusion of control through market analogies. Treich (2022) similarly critiques the axiomatic foundations of welfare economics, highlighting the inability of standard models to grapple with irreversibility, uncertainty, and non-substitutability.

The Review's intellectual genealogy is rooted in environmental economics rather than ecological economics. This distinction matters. Environmental economics seeks to correct externalities within market logic, while ecological economics questions the epistemological and normative basis of that logic itself. As Raina (2021) argues, Dasgupta's ambition to transform economics from within is undermined by its refusal to relinquish optimisation as the primary mode of reasoning. By embedding biodiversity within intertemporal cost-benefit frameworks, the Review reproduces a vision of the future that remains economically overdetermined.

What emerges is not a rupture but a recalibration of HM Treasury orthodoxy. The Review's emphasis on "natural capital maintenance" retools fiscal conservatism into ecological language. This move permits a performative display of reform while safeguarding Treasury's gatekeeping role over macroeconomic policy and public investment. The institutional logic remains intact, even as the policy rhetoric evolves.

Critics have also drawn attention to the Review's methodological silences. Priyadarshini et al. (2022) observe that participatory epistemologies, indigenous knowledge systems, and feminist critiques of valuation are marginalised. These absences are not accidental but symptomatic of a deeper epistemic closure within Treasury thinking. Valuation is imagined as a technical problem of measurement and integration, rather than a contested practice entangled with politics, culture, and power. Maechler and Boisvert (2024) further explore this critique, arguing that the "new spirit of conservation" merely reinscribes market-centric rationalities under a more progressive idiom.

Conventional policy frameworks such as HM Treasury's Green Book are further compromised by their implicit acceptance of shifting ecological baselines (Pauly, 1995). As Groom and Turk (2021) and Scott and Parker (2024) argue, each generation normalises degraded ecosystems, leading to institutional amnesia about the true extent of biodiversity loss. This renders present-day land-use decisions blind to historical ecological richness, compounding the Green Book's discounting of long-term value with a failure to recognise what has already been lost, a concern underscored in public-health terms by Dr Joseph O'Keeffe, a General Practice trainee (O'Keeffe, J, 2025, pers.comm.). By contrast, O-P-G as a TRM affords foregrounding these hidden trajectories of decline, resisting baseline amnesia and restoring contextual integrity to ecological decision-making.

Newer empirical studies reinforce these concerns. Jonäll et al. (2025) identify the institutional risks of financialising biodiversity through investment logics that may displace local knowledges and affect equitable governance. Likewise, Trimanto et al. (2025) propose a “degree of separation” framework that rejects proximity-based valuation in favour of situated, interspecies ethics. Meanwhile, Scott et al. (2024) interrogates the practical implications of such conceptual shifts within planning frameworks, questioning whether biodiversity crisis narratives are being meaningfully integrated into institutional cultures of land-use governance.

At the legal and other implementation levels, Anthony (2025) and Atkins et al. (2025) show that while local governance structures (e.g. Local Nature Recovery Strategies in England) seek to embed collaborative participation, they often operate under centralised frameworks that still privilege HM Treasury-defined metrics. These findings align with O-P-G’s contention that technocratic centralism persists beneath the rhetoric of stakeholder inclusion.

In the context of CCLUPs, such economisation becomes performative. Furthermore, Green Book orthodoxy persists in treating environmental value through monetised proxies and contingent valuation methods, flattening ecological specificity into abstract economic units. This critique is echoed by the UK’s Natural Capital Committee in its final response to the 25-Year Environment Plan, which underscores the epistemic failure of economic orthodoxy to apprehend the systemic, non-substitutable nature of ecological degradation (Natural Capital Committee, 2023). HM Treasury Green Book methodologies are structurally incapable of capturing the relational, affective, and contested dynamics that characterise real-world deliberation is found empirically in CCLUPs.

As Tait (2024) argues, efforts to integrate natural capital into policy remain constrained by the Treasury’s economistic logic, which prioritises abstract calculability over the messiness of social contestation and situated environmental values. Collier (2024) contends that the HM Treasury’s approach reflects not only a failure of imagination but a structural incapacity to accommodate moral pluralism. The repeated invocation of biodiversity “loss” as a market failure masks the ontological violence of framing nonhuman life as capital. What appears as prudent stewardship is, on closer inspection, an epistemic violence that translates living systems into spreadsheet-compatible formats.

In sum, the numerous concerns and critiques above, and that of Faith's (2021) of the HM Treasury commissioned Dasgupta Review exemplifies “organised hypocrisy” (Brunsson, 1989): in this case the performative alignment with environmental discourse without disrupting the calculative core of governance. Its technocratic appeal is precisely what renders it politically palatable and intellectually inert. O-P-G as a TRM does not seek to replace economic reasoning, but to provincialise it-to situate it as one epistemic frame among many, and to recover the matters of concern (Latour, 2004) it effaces. Only by embracing plural

modes of understanding can the moral and ecological stakes of contested land-use be adequately engaged.

6. Citizen and Post-Normal Science as Participatory Realism¹²

Unsurprisingly, few policymakers today would openly oppose participation. From Abraham Lincoln's ideal of "government of the people, by the people, for the people," to contemporary visions of co-production and civic empowerment, participation is widely valorised in democracies across the world. Yet in practice, participatory initiatives often fall short bounded by proceduralism, constrained by technocracy, and subordinated to predefined economic logics (Wynne, 2007; Stirling, 2008) such as the HM Treasury's Green Book as discussed above. In this context, citizen science-defined as the systematic involvement of non-professionals in scientific inquiry, first formalised in the United States in the 1990s (Bonney et al., 2009)-emerges not merely as a tool for public engagement or data collection, but as a methodologically plural site that offers alternatives to the epistemic and ethical constraints of the Green Book with respect to CCLUPs by addressing deeper questions of expertise, inclusion, and authority.

Notably, citizen science foregrounds this ethos. Projects like iNaturalist, the UK Phenology Network, and the Community Air Quality Monitoring Programme, amongst others, involve thousands of volunteers in the collection, interpretation, and contextualisation of ecological data (Bonney et al., 2014; Cooper et al., 2007; Follett and Strezov, 2015). These initiatives challenge the hierarchies that place professional science above lay observation, inviting what Irwin (1995) called "the citizen scientist"-not as a naïve amateur, but as an engaged epistemic actor whose lived experience, local knowledge, and normative commitments enrich the knowledge commons.

Several models of citizen science now exist. Bonney et al. (2009) proposed three: contributory (citizens collect data), collaborative (citizens also analyse), and co-created (citizens help shape research questions). More recently, Salmon et al. (2021) introduced a tripartite model of citizens, scientists, and enablers, each with distinct but overlapping roles. These schemas illuminate how citizen science can range from tokenistic engagement to deep co-production. The question, as always, is who decides the terms of participation and what counts as valid knowledge.

¹² I use the term participatory realism as an umbrella concept to suggest that knowledge, reality, and value emerge through situated interaction and co-construction between humans and the world - a view aligned with both citizen and post-normal science and many other transdisciplinary methodologies.

The rhetoric of “evidence-based policymaking” continues to invoke a narrow image of transactional and instrumental expertise grounded in probabilistic certainty, scale, and abstraction (Jasanoff, 2003; Leach et al., 2005). Yet many of the most consequential challenges of our time-biodiversity collapse, climate displacement, systemic inequality-resist such narrow and insufficient representation. As Blanden and Macmillan (2016) demonstrate in the domain of educational mobility, structural inequalities persist even amid expansion, revealing how underlying social conditions constrain intergenerational opportunity and voice. These dynamics are mirrored in CCLUPs, where patterns of exclusion shape whose ecological futures are considered and whose are foreclosed.

CCLUPs represent a social phenomenon that are what Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) called “post-normal”, where facts are uncertain, stakes high, and decisions on the use of the land are urgent. Under such conditions, public participation is not optional or ancillary-and even if it mandated, it remains fundamentally constitutive of robust, ethical inquiry. As Mike Hulme (2011) argues, the legitimacy of knowledge depends not only on its technical accuracy but also on how it is situated, debated, and used in public life. This epistemological rigidity remains deeply embedded, as very recently and empirically evidenced by a recent presentation by an Oxbridge-trained economist within the Scottish Government, which, despite its framing around “collective intelligence,” ultimately reaffirmed the predictive, metric-driven logics and microfoundational assumptions emblematic of HM Treasury orthodoxy (Wilkinson, 2025)¹³ Though framed in the language of network science and “collective intelligence,” the presentation’s emphasis on quantifiable metrics for trust, agility, and productivity merely reasserts a deterministic logic of prediction and control-hallmarks of Treasury economics-within an analytic costume. Its delivery in Edinburgh, geographically, culturally, and institutionally distant from Westminster, further evidences the deep institutional entrenchment of this epistemology, despite rhetorical nods to complexity and culture.

Consideration then, of participatory epistemic practices of citizen and post-normal science - as participatory realism, - to the limitations of the Green Book is particularly salient in the context of CCLUPs, where decisions about nature, economy, and community collide. Projects like the on-going NHS Velindre Cancer Centre or the Woodhouse Colliery are not only about short-term land-use decisions *per se*-they are about meaning, belonging, and ecological futures- for the long-term, indeed, for future generations yet unborn. In such cases, conventional public consultations-often held late, framed narrowly, and dominated by “sound science”-often exacerbates mistrust of so-called 'experts'. Participatory realism, by contrast, insists that affected communities are not just stakeholders but co-interpretive agents. As Gabrys (2016) suggests, digital sensors and data platforms ought to be embedded

¹³ Wilkinson, T. (2025) *Collective Intelligence and Network Microfoundations*, SDS Hub Seminar, University of Edinburgh, 7 May 2025.

in civic practices that allow for deliberation, dissent, and plural valuation¹⁴, together with programmes of learning and knowledge about biodiversity and ecology for citizens in general.

This perspective also challenges the notion of participation as purely rational or procedural. It includes the affective and embodied dimensions of ecological engagement: grief over loss, attachment to place, anger at exclusion. Climate anxiety—defined as psychological distress linked to awareness of climate change and institutional inaction—and eco-anxiety—a broader response to ecological degradation marked by grief and solastalgia¹⁵—are increasingly recognised among younger cohorts (Hickman et al., 2021). Cosh et al., (2024) document how adolescent eco-anxiety intersects with emotional regulation and psychiatric frameworks, by systematically investigating the potential clinical recognition of eco-anxiety as a planetary health issue. Frick et al. (2024) position climate anxiety as an adaptive, existentially grounded response. Körner et al. (2024) identify a spectrum of climate distress among European students, shaped by cultural coping practices. Whitmee et al. (2024) frame eco-anxiety as symptomatic of institutional and intergenerational failure. Together, these contributions underscore that climate and eco-anxieties are neither marginal nor irrational—they are structurally embedded, medically consequential, and politically salient matters of concern.

In such contexts, participation is not merely a matter of input—it is a matter of care, or in Latour's (2004) terms, a response to matters of concern. Participatory realism thus goes beyond deliberative democracy¹⁶; it demands epistemic justice¹⁷.

As argued above, HM Treasury's Green Book, the Dasgupta Review, and most mainstream planning logics remain structurally ill-equipped to accommodate the claimed affordances of participatory realism in the case of CCLUPs. They remain narrowly anchored to evaluative metrics that systematically exclude non-market values—including the affective and moral

¹⁴ Plural valuation recognises the diversity of ways in which nature is valued, including ecological, cultural, spiritual, and relational dimensions—challenging frameworks that rely solely on monetary or instrumental assessments (IPBES, 2022)

¹⁵ Solastalgia describes the emotional or existential distress experienced when one's home environment is under threat, coined to capture place-based ecological grief (Albrecht et al., 2007)

¹⁶ Deliberative democracy foregrounds inclusive, focused, and reasoned public discourse as a prerequisite to democratic decision-making, positioning such deliberation as foundational to the legitimacy of governance—particularly where contested values and uncertain socio-ecological futures are at stake (Dryzek, 2000). It has been institutionalised in several democratic jurisdictions outside the UK, with Ireland standing out for its application to biodiversity and ecological loss in major infrastructure planning.

¹⁷ Epistemic justice involves fairness in recognising diverse ways of knowing and valuing contributions from all knowledge holders—particularly in relation to environmental governance, where Indigenous and local knowledges are often marginalised (Fricker, 2007).

dimensions of biodiversity and ecological loss—and reduce ethical complexity to calculable terms through cost–benefit analyses and discounting mechanisms. These structural limitations expose the inability of orthodox appraisal methodologies not merely to accommodate complexity, but to perceive the social and epistemic dynamics most consequential to public legitimacy. It is precisely in response to this epistemic deficit that Open-Praxis-Graph (O-P-G) as a TRM finds its relevance—offering not only a critique of dominant frameworks, but a demonstrable capacity to render legible the contested, emergent, and digitally mediated dimensions of public decision-making. Comparable ambitions are evident in the Mainstreaming Green Infrastructure project, which advocates for place-based, cross-sectoral planning frameworks capable of integrating ecological, social, and epistemic complexity (MainstreamingGI, 2023). By contrast to the argued and numerous insufficiencies of HM Treasury orthodoxy when trying to understand CCLUPs, O-P-G as TRM engages with socially embedded meaning-making and digital materiality, aligning with recent work that highlights the role of network topology in the amplification of disinformation. I therefore contend that what is needed is a research methodology that can detect, interpret, and respond to the embedded, dynamic, and pluralistic conditions through which contestation and legitimacy actually unfold, in near real-time to facilitate timely decision-making. In response, Open-Praxis-Graph (O-P-G) as a Transdisciplinary Research Methodology (TRM) offers more than a critique of the Green Book’s instrumental and reductive logic as applied to Climate-Contested Land Use Projects (CCLUPs). It represents an ontologically distinct alternative. This approach is grounded in practice rather than in policy. It privileges lived praxis over statistical proxies. O-P-G is simultaneously aligned with the epistemological commitments of participatory realism and the normative ideals of deliberative democracy.

It enables empirical granularity through the systematic analysis of openly accessible digital and social data. At the same time, it provides a framework for theoretically informed and pragmatically oriented reflexivity. This reflexivity is not confined to academic researchers. It is communicable across stakeholder domains.

Through graphical and visual syntheses, O-P-G traces and renders legible evolving epistemic and affective alignments. These visual outputs surface the social dynamics of CCLUPs in real time. They reveal insights into the social dynamics of how practices of knowing, valuing, and acting generate, stabilise, or contest legitimacy within complex decision-making environments.

7. Citizen Biodiversity Learning and the Moral Imperative

Despite the rhetorical centrality of nature in UK climate narratives, there remains a glaring policy lacuna: the systematic absence of citizen-facing biodiversity and ecological learning initiatives, particularly those sponsored or mandated by the state. Whereas climate mitigation is often translated into quantifiable behavioural guidance—turn down the

thermostat, drive less, fly less-the moral and epistemic claims of biodiversity loss remain uninternalised within most civic institutions. This void is particularly pronounced in England, where formal schooling largely fails to incorporate sustained ecological literacy (Royal Society, 2022), and where biodiversity citizenship remains a largely aspirational concept (House of Lords, 2023).

This democratic deficit is epistemologically significant. Citizen science-defined as the structured participation of non-professionals in scientific knowledge-making-has, since its formal emergence in the United States in the 1990s, offered an alternative to the instrumental logic of expert-driven metrics (Bonney et al., 2009). While Section 6 outlined its epistemic and ontological commitments, here we emphasise its unrealised potential within the UK's biodiversity policy infrastructure. The Green Book, as discussed, remains structurally unable to account for affective, moral, or place-based values. Nor do current UK Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) policies, despite their regulatory prominence, resolve this blind spot. Indeed, they instead illustrates the technocratic commodification of nature. While mandating biodiversity calculation and 'offsetting' ostensibly advances environmental accountability, leading critiques highlight that BNG frameworks risk masking ongoing ecological degradation under a veneer of calculative equivalence (Maron et.al, 2018; Sullivan, 2017). Biodiversity offsetting schemes tend to treat ecosystems as fungible, replaceable assets to be traded, (Wauchope, Bull, and Milner-Gulland, 2024) thereby risking oversimplifying complex ecological relationships and undermining the unique value of individual ecosystems.

In contrast, citizen science-particularly when co-designed with communities during proactive consultation and meaningful engagement-cultivates modes of attentiveness, care, and shared intelligibility that cannot be reduced to net gain scores or monetised carbon equivalents. Empirical studies have shown that such participatory practices deepen ecological attachment, foster stewardship ethics, and enable the translation of complex ecological data into locally salient knowledge (Bonney et al., 2014; Cooper et al., 2007; Gabrys, 2016). Yet in the UK, citizen biodiversity learning remains largely voluntary, fragmented, and under-supported. Unlike Scandinavian and Baltic states, where school-based biodiversity monitoring and public ecological literacy campaigns have long been normalised, (Yli-Panula et al., 2019) the UK has not institutionalised ecological learning as a national civic priority.

This omission has serious implications for CCLUPs. When local communities are excluded from meaningful ecological knowledge production, democratic legitimacy is undermined. In such contexts, citizen science is not a luxury-it is a moral and political necessity. As Stirling (2008) has argued, robust governance under conditions of uncertainty requires not less public participation, but more-especially when normative stakes are high, and knowledge is contested. Yet UK state-led programmes that embed such participation into ecological planning remain elusive. Instead, ecological awareness is outsourced to NGOs, ad-hoc funding schemes, or charismatic individual projects that struggle to scale. To move beyond tokenism and technocracy, the United Kingdom ought to cultivate a new culture of biodiversity

citizenship. This requires embedding ecological literacy at every stage of formal education, linked to practical, participatory experiences of local ecosystems. It demands reframing biodiversity not as a technical object but as a moral and civic concern, integral to democratic life, and I argue, following (Unterhitzberger, et al., 2024) a duty of the UK's 'responsible researchers and practitioners'.

O-P-G as a TRM, introduced throughout this essay, offers a learning and educational framework for addressing this deficit. By tracing how material arrangements, rule systems, and local intelligibility coalesce within specific practices, O-P-G reconfigures participatory realism, as conceptualised and argued for above, not as an instrumental tool of outreach but as a method of co-governance based on citizen-based understanding, learning and contextualised education. . When applied as an interrogative TRM, O-P-G fosters dialogical, discursive, and dialectical modes of civic engagement for all citizens that align with contemporary educational theories of participatory and experiential learning (Bonney et al., 2009; Gabrys, 2016; Sustainability, 2017) about biodiversity and ecology loss. These approaches have been successfully institutionalised in countries such as Sweden and New Zealand, where national biodiversity strategies incorporate community-led learning, traditional ecological knowledge, and citizen involvement in governance processes (Hägglund and Johansson, 2020; Aotearoa New Zealand Biodiversity Strategy, 2020). If ecological crisis is to be addressed not merely as a matter of policy but as a matter of public meaning, then O-P-G aligns with a broader moral imperative-one in which biodiversity and ecological learning is not the preserve of experts, but the participatory deliberative democratic right of all of citizens.

8. Towards a New Practical Intelligibility

The unprecedented convergence of ecological crisis, digital transformation, and political uncertainty demands not merely technical reform, but ontological recalibration. Traditional models of governance -such as those prescribed and mandated by HM Treasury orthodoxies premised on linear causality, economic instrumentalism, and institutional compartmentalisation - are no longer adequate to grasp the emergent realities and social dynamics of CCLUPs as conceptualised as social phenomenon. As a social theorist and philosopher, Schatzki (2002; 2025) argues, social life unfolds not in discrete causal chains but in an intricate, entangled "practice plenum" - a dense field of interwoven activities, material arrangements, sayings, doings, affectivities and goals.

In this section, I theorise how adopting Schatzki's 'flat' practice-plenum ontology can provide a richer 'practical intelligibility' - as a unique Schatzki term, for CCLUPs and the crises they index, especially as these projects, both in the UK and beyond are increasingly shaped by digital epistemic objects, globalised moral imperatives, and intergenerational anxieties.

Legacy governance ontologies, such as those of HM Treasury, grounded in Cartesian dualisms and Enlightenment rationality, seek to isolate problems, quantify variables, and optimise outcomes through mechanistic intervention (Flyvbjerg and Gardner, 2023; Coyle, 2020). In the context of CCLUPs, I have argued that this logic manifests in the dominance of cost-benefit analyses, net biodiversity gain calculators, and risk matrices that presume a detached, managerial relationship to the biosphere.

Yet the reality of actual and recent UK CCLUPs like the NHS Velindre Cancer Centre's, as empirically evidenced using a specific progenitor of the current O-P-G methodology (O'Keeffe, et al., 2025, Forthcoming) contested development, or the Woodhouse Colliery or Ireland's halted motorway expansions through ancient woodlands (Irish Citizens' Assembly, 2023), illustrates that land-use conflicts are not technical puzzles but socially saturated, morally charged, temporally complex assemblages.

Here, traditional forms of project management and business case intelligibility - grounded in prediction, monetisation, and control - falter. They are unable to accommodate the indeterminacy, contestation, and emotional intensities that suffuse CCLUPs.

The methodological advantage of O-P-G as a TRM lies in its capacity to render visible the situated, affective, and materially mediated dynamics of CCLUPs that remain imperceptible to HM Treasury orthodoxy. As shown in the analysis of the #SaveTheNorthernMeadows campaign (O'Keeffe et al., 2025, Forthcoming), NodeXL mapping revealed the centrality of disinformation nodes—actors deploying coordinated digital messaging, often aligned with Extinction Rebellion tactics, to shape public discourse. Such communicative asymmetries are structurally invisible to rationalist appraisal frameworks that presume linearity, neutrality, and decontextualised input-output logic. By contrast, O-P-G as a TRM enables researchers to remain vigilant to the social and epistemic conditions under which disinformation is likely to emerge, offering not only empirical insight but also a reflexive orientation toward digitally mediated contestation (Ahmed and Lugović 2019; Ahmed and Smith, 2023; Khan et al., 2022).

Schatzki's (2002) concept of the "practice plenum" offers a profound ontological alternative. Rather than envisioning social reality as a field of individuated agents and discrete objects, the practice plenum posits a world constituted by nexuses of practices and material arrangements.

In this view:

- Governance is not an act imposed upon a passive world, but a situated, ongoing performance within an already active material-discursive nexus¹⁸.
- Practical intelligibility (i.e.) emerges not from abstract calculation, but from the relational coherence of doings, sayings, and material mediations.
- CCLUPs are not isolated interventions but local condensations of global practices of care, exploitation, resistance, and hope.
- This shift demands epistemic humility from current UK policy and its makers and agents. It acknowledges that no single viewpoint - whether that of the project manager, activist, planner, or policy-maker - can fully apprehend the whole.

The digital revolution further complicates and intensifies the practice plenum. As Schatzki (2025) argues, digital technologies have become material actors in their own right, reshaping temporalities, spatialities, and relationalities.

In CCLUPs, this manifests vividly:

- Digital platforms such as Twitter (now X), Instagram, and local WhatsApp groups function as epistemic infrastructures, enabling real-time mobilisation, storytelling, surveillance, and counter-surveillance (Gabrys, 2016).
- Hashtags like #SaveTheNorthernMeadows crystallise affective solidarities and new publics, simultaneously local and transnational.
- Knowledge is no longer monopolised by institutions but distributed across heterogeneous networks of activists, experts, citizens, and AI-generated narratives.
- This proliferation of digital material arrangements demands new forms of governance intelligibility - ones that can map and respond to fluid, fragmented, multi-scalar contestations without reducing them to noise or externalities.

The climate crisis amplifies the urgency of ontological rethinking. As Clayton et al. (2017); Hickman et al. (2021) and Cosh et al. (2024) demonstrate, younger generations are experiencing profound eco-anxiety, rooted not only in material degradation but in the perceived epistemic and moral failures of current governance systems.

A practice-plenum ontology invites a governance ethic responsive to this crisis:

¹⁸ The material-discursive nexus refers to the interplay of physical arrangements (e.g., infrastructure, technology) and social meaning-making practices, particularly how one conditions or reveals the other (Barad, 2003)

- It foregrounds relationality over abstraction, meaning over metrics, care over control.
- It demands that policymakers, researchers, and citizens see themselves not as detached observers but as embedded participants in the very networks they seek to steer.
- It aligns with calls for "mission-oriented" governance (Mazzucato, 2021), but deepens them by recognising that missions ought to be co-constructed within plural, contested, and affectively charged fields of practice. As Maechler and Boisvert (2024) argue, valuation-dominated regimes risk crowding out moral and political engagement, reducing complex ecological entanglements to technocratic artefacts of measurement and trade-off.

In this essay, O-P-G as a TRM is operationalised, in part, through the analytical lens of practice theory - drawing substantively, though not exclusively, on the work of Schatzki. While Schatzki's account offers a fertile ontological and conceptual apparatus for apprehending the practical intelligibility of social life within CCLUPs, O-P-G *per se* is not delimited by any singular articulation of practice theory. Rather, it embraces the inherent heterogeneity and pluralism of the wider constellation of practice-theoretical traditions, and seeks to instantiate a methodology responsive to the contextual demands of particular research questions-tracing activity chains, material entanglements, and saying-doing nexuses that are typically effaced by deterministic explanatory models (O'Keeffe, et al., 2024, manuscript submitted).

When applied to CCLUPs, I contend that O-P-G as a TRM, as applied in this essay, affords the capacity to:

- Reveal how project trajectories are shaped by silent absences as much as by loud declarations.
- Map how material arrangements (e.g., fences, digital maps, biodiversity and ecological and other environmental surveys, drone surveillance, websites, blogs, online media news) are not neutral but active material objects in such contestation.
- Show how affective atmospheres¹⁹ - grief, anger, hope, anxiety, angst, sense of duty, amongst others - circulate and congeal around specific sites and practices.
- Thus, O-P-G as a TRM not only diagnoses the shortcomings of legacy governance intelligibility but prefigures more reflexive, responsive, and morally attuned forms of practice.

¹⁹ Affective atmospheres describe the ambient, non-discursive fields of mood or emotion that emerge collectively and relationally within spaces of action, protest, or deliberation (Anderson, 2009; Wylie, 2007)

In confronting the epistemic and governance challenges posed by CCLUPs, responsible policymakers, researchers and practitioners ought to relinquish the persistent fantasy of detached mastery sustained by HM Treasury orthodoxy and mirrored in public-sector departments in other democracies structurally beholden to its logics of control and calculability. In its place, I contend, all stakeholders ought to cultivate a plural, situated, and materially attuned mode of practical intelligibility—one that foregrounds the affective charge, temporal volatility, and socio-material complexity through which project governance in the case of CCLUPs is enacted. Such a paradigm would enable more reflexive, responsive, and contextually grounded land-use decision-making in near-real time.

Schatzki's practice plenum, enriched by attention to digital infrastructures and climate moral imperatives, offers a compelling ontological ground for this rethinking. O-P-G as a TRM operationalises this vision methodologically, providing tools not for controlling the future, but for navigating, with humility and care, its emergent possibilities.

In the contested terrains of CCLUPs, and beyond, the future of UK public-sector infrastructure project governance depends on our willingness, as researchers and practitioners to rise to its challenges, change the status quo to see, listen, and act differently by considering supplementary methodological alternatives such as O-P-G as a TRM.

9. Conclusion: Rewriting Project Governance as Performance in Climate Contested Land-Use Projects

This essay has argued that project governance in UK biodiversity and ecological land-use decisions for public-sector infrastructure projects is not merely compromised by technical shortfalls or economic misalignment, but by a deeper performative adherence to epistemic scripts that foreclose alternative understandings of value, risk, inclusion, and intergenerational justice²⁰. These scripts-rooted in deterministic economic rationalism and exemplified by the performative orthodoxy of HM Treasury's Green Book-operate through the staging of procedural legitimacy, calculative reasoning, and institutional neutrality. Yet this staging, as rhetorically exemplified in the pivotal rehearsal scene of *Tár*, often functions to disqualify alternative knowledges, obscure moral complexity, and ignore or diminish the valid matters of concern voiced by younger generations. Schuitema and Lacchia (2025) found that children aged 10 to 12 perceive climate change as a psychologically distant threat, which hampers their ability to employ effective coping strategies, thereby exacerbating feelings of anxiety and helplessness. The lived climate and eco-anxiety experience of Gen Z and Gen

²⁰ Intergenerational justice asserts that present generations bear ethical responsibilities toward future generations—particularly in relation to climate change, biodiversity loss, and planetary boundaries (Gosseries & Meyer, 2009)

Alpha increasingly manifests not only in affective distress, but in civil disobedience, digital activism, and costly legal manoeuvres—a socio-political reality governance systems can no longer afford to sideline (Hickman et al., 2021).

Against this backdrop, the essay has proposed the O-P-G as a TRM designed to attend to these insufficiencies for use in CCLUPs. O-P-G as a TRM does not claim panacea status. Rather, it fosters new ways of seeing and organising project governance by making practical intelligibility, practical reason, and material-discursive entanglements central to how decisions unfold. It shifts the centre of analytical gravity from universalising logics to site-specific practice architectures, within a flat ontology, thereby enabling scholars and practitioners to recognise the relational, affective, and epistemic dimensions and understand the complexities of social dynamics of the project governance in CCLUPs.

Crucially, O-P-G as TRM aligns with the pedagogical and deliberative potential of post-normal science and citizen science, not as methodologies per se, but as knowledge cultures that foreground uncertainty, plurality, and democratic learning. As shown in international exemplars—from biodiversity learning frameworks in Finland and New Zealand, to Ireland's Citizens' Assembly on biodiversity loss—democratically engaged publics can reframe ecological governance as a civic good, not merely a technical burden. O-P-G as a TRM when mobilised in such settings, serves, as shown empirically, not only research aims but ethical and pedagogical ones: to equip publics, especially youth, with tools to interrogate, shape, and co-produce decisions that affect both biosphere and lifeworld towards more informed land-use decision making in near real-time via discourse and written and graphical means.

This essay's key takeaway is thus ***not simply a call for better contested land-use decisions affecting biodiversity and ecological loss, but for different ways of deciding***. Ways that resist the elitist paternalism and the legacy of implicit unilateralism embedded in the UK's HM Treasury's current prescribed and mandated economic orthodoxy in the case of CCLUPs. Ways that honour the plurality of human and more-than-human interests. Ways that treat practical intelligibility as a condition of democratic legitimacy, and citizen participation not as consultation but as co-production and a participatory realism. The Woodhouse Colliery and NHS Velindre cases—alongside, *en passant* projects like the Irish motorway scheme²¹—show that failure to do so creates avoidable significant delays and costs and instead fosters, reputational risk, and epistemic injustice and civil disobedience.

In sum, the thesis and its argument I have set out and advanced here is not merely a critique but a normative proposal. For UK researchers and practitioners, especially those engaging in project-based governance of public-sector projects that encounter Climate Contested land

²¹ For a detailed examination of the M3 motorway controversy and its implications for heritage preservation, see Reynolds (2005).

use, there is an ethical duty to look beyond calculative closure and consider alternatives that sustain democratic accountability. Responsible researchers and practitioners of sustainability ought to challenge dominant appraisal orthodoxies such as the Green Book, not out of obligation to rule or convention, but from an authentic commitment to disclosing what matters in ecologically and socially contested land-use decisions. O-P-G as a TRM offers one such alternative: not as a heuristic device²², but as a principled and reflexive methodology attuned to the plural realities of the Anthropocene. It invites a shift in both governance and research practice—towards more dialogical, deliberative, and dignified ways of facing our shared ecological futures.

By closing in this manner, this essay directly echoes the call of the SEEDS 2025 Conference for new methodologies and novel analytical lenses capable of grasping the ethical, epistemological, and participatory complexities of sustainability transitions. In proposing O-P-G as a TRM grounded in the material-discursive textures of actual projects, it offers precisely the sort of transdisciplinary engagement SEEDS promotes: one that is conceptually rigorous, empirically sensitive, and oriented toward inclusive and just ecological futures.

In this context, the UK Government's recent accelerative shift—manifest in its 'Agenda for Growth'-driven planning reforms and the curtailment of protest rights—ought not to be mistaken for mere technocratic expediency. Rather, these developments risk signalling the early contours of a democratic retreat²³. As the second President of the United States and a principal architect of American republicanism, John Adams starkly warned, "There never was a democracy yet that did not commit suicide" (Adams, 1814). For responsible researchers and practitioners alike, the imperative is to resist any drift toward a form of administrative authoritarianism²⁴ that marginalises public deliberation and renders biodiversity and ecological justice expendable. To do so is not to indulge in moral grandstanding, but to meet the civic urgency of sustaining democratic lifeworlds²⁵ in an age of unrelenting ecological

²² While O-P-G offers a heuristic structure for inquiry, it is framed here not merely as a conceptual guide but as a transdisciplinary research methodology — a structured yet flexible epistemological and methodological approach.

²³ Democratic retreat describes the erosion of inclusive public reasoning processes in policymaking—often replaced by procedural formalism, managerialism, or populist instrumentalism (Dryzek, 2000) as the anti-thesis of deliberative democracy (Mansbridge et al., 2012).

²⁴ Administrative authoritarianism refers to the centralisation of decision-making within technocratic institutions or state apparatuses, often at the expense of deliberative democracy and civic participation (Fischer, 2000).

²⁵ Democratic lifeworlds denote the lived spaces and social processes through which citizens engage in collective meaning-making, mutual recognition, and political agency (Habermas, 1987).

destabilisation and pervasive digital mediation-an obligation owed not only to our present citizenry, but to the young and unborn generations who inherit our decisions.

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